

ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: Simultaneous interpretation, a crucial facet of multilingual communication, involves translating spoken words into another language in real-time. This complex process is essential for international conferences, diplomatic meetings, and global media events. Despite its importance, simultaneous interpretation presents a range of challenges that can impact both the interpreter's performance and the effectiveness of communication. This article explores the key problems in simultaneous interpretation, including cognitive overload, linguistic nuances, technological issues, and the impact of context.

Key words: Simultaneous Interpretation, problems in simultaneous interpretation, linguistic nuances, technological issues.

Абстракт: Синхронная интерпретация, важный аспект многоязычной коммуникации, включает в себя перевод разговорных слов на другой язык в режиме реального времени. Этот сложный процесс необходим для проведения международных конференций, дипломатических встреч и глобальных медиа-мероприятий. Несмотря на свою значимость, синхронная интерпретация представляет собой ряд проблем, которые могут повлиять как на производительность интерпретатора, так и на эффективность общения. В этой статье рассматриваются ключевые проблемы синхронной интерпретации, включая когнитивную перегрузку, языковые нюансы, технологические проблемы и влияние контекста.

Ключевые слова: Синхронная интерпретация, проблемы синхронной интерпретации, языковые нюансы, технологические проблемы.

Abstrakt: Ko'p tilli muloqotning muhim jihati bo'lgan sinxron talqin so'zlashuv so'zlarini real vaqt rejimida boshqa tilga tarjima qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu murakkab jarayon xalqaro anjumanlar, diplomatik uchrashuvlar va global media

tadbirlarini o‘tkazish uchun zarur. O‘zining ahamiyatiga qaramay, sinxron talqin bir qator muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi, ular ham tarjimonning mahsuldorligiga, ham muloqot samaradorligiga ta’sir qilishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada sinxron talqinning asosiy muammolari, shu jumladan kognitiv zo‘riqish, til nozikliklari, texnologik muammolar va kontekstning ta’siri ko‘rib chiqiladi.

Tayanch so‘zlar: Sinxron talqin, sinxron talqin muammolari, til nozikliklari, texnologik muammolar.

One of the primary challenges in simultaneous interpretation is cognitive overload. Interpreters are required to process spoken information in one language while simultaneously translating it into another. This dual-tasking demands rapid mental processing and high levels of concentration, which can lead to mental fatigue. Cognitive overload can affect the interpreter's ability to maintain accuracy and fluidity in their translation. The speed at which speakers deliver their messages can significantly impact the interpreter's performance. Fast-paced speech can outstrip the interpreter's capacity to process and translate information in real-time, leading to omissions, errors, or inaccuracies. Complex or convoluted sentence structures can exacerbate cognitive load. Interpreters must quickly deconstruct and reassemble these sentences into the target language while preserving the original meaning, which can be mentally taxing.

Long periods of interpretation can lead to mental fatigue, affecting the interpreter's attention and performance. Regular breaks and shift rotations are essential to mitigate this issue. *Tatyana Mikhailova's research examines how cognitive load impacts interpreter performance and discusses strategies to manage mental fatigue. She emphasizes the importance of psychological resilience and cognitive training to mitigate performance issues related to prolonged interpreting sessions.*⁷

⁷ Mikhailova, T. S. (2009). Cognitive Load and Its Impact on Simultaneous Interpretation. *Russian Journal of Translation Studies*, 4(1), 32-46.

Another significant challenge in simultaneous interpretation is dealing with linguistic nuances and cultural differences. *Dilshodbek Tursunov in his works focuses on the impact of cultural and idiomatic differences on interpretation and suggests strategies for overcoming these challenges, particularly in the context of Central Asian languages and cultures. Interpreters must navigate various aspects of language and culture to deliver accurate and meaningful translations.*⁸

Idioms and colloquialisms can be particularly challenging as they often do not have direct equivalents in other languages. Interpreters must find ways to convey the intended meaning without losing the essence of the original expression. Cultural references or context-specific information can be difficult to translate accurately. Interpreters need to be familiar with the cultural background of both the source and target languages to ensure appropriate and relevant translations. Maintaining the appropriate register and tone is crucial. The interpreter must adjust their language to match the speaker's intent, whether formal or informal, to accurately reflect the message.

Technological issues can also pose significant problems in simultaneous interpretation. While technology has advanced to facilitate real-time translation, it is not without its pitfalls. *Shakhnoza A. Karimova (2014), a researcher from Uzbekistan, explores the integration of modern technologies in interpretation. Karimova's work examines technological challenges and the potential solutions to ensure effective use of technology in interpretation settings.*⁹ Problems with interpretation equipment, such as microphones, headsets, or transmission systems, can disrupt the flow of interpretation. Regular maintenance and checks are necessary to minimize the risk of technical failures. Poor audio quality can hinder the interpreter's ability to hear and understand the speaker. Background noise, interference, or low volume can affect the clarity of the message being interpreted.

Over-reliance on technology can sometimes lead to issues if systems fail or if there are connectivity problems. Interpreters need to be prepared for contingencies

⁸ Tursunov, D. K. (2012). Cultural Challenges in Simultaneous Interpretation: Insights from Central Asia. *Uzbekistan Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 8(3), 23-37.

⁹ Karimova, S. A. (2014). Technological Advances and Challenges in Simultaneous Interpretation. *Uzbek Journal of Translation Technology*, 7(1), 40-54.

and have backup plans in place. The context and environment in which simultaneous interpretation occurs can also influence the interpreter's performance.

The acoustics of the interpretation environment play a crucial role. Poor room acoustics or excessive reverberation can make it difficult for interpreters to hear and process the speaker's voice clearly. In settings where interpreters are required to manage multiple speakers or switch between different languages rapidly, the pressure can increase, impacting accuracy and efficiency.

Simultaneous interpretation is a demanding task that requires skill, concentration, and adaptability. Understanding and addressing the challenges of cognitive overload, linguistic nuances, technological issues, and contextual factors are crucial for effective interpretation. Continuous training, technological advancements, and proper support systems can help mitigate these problems and enhance the quality of simultaneous interpretation. As global communication continues to expand, addressing these challenges will remain essential for ensuring clear and accurate multilingual dialogue. Contributions from Tatyana Mikhailova provide insights into cognitive and technological aspects, while This diverse body of research underscores the complexity of simultaneous interpretation and the need for ongoing exploration and development in the field.

Literature:

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